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Year 1

Year 2

Year 3

Year 4

Year 5

Structure, functionality, data inputs and outputs of the Toolbox

Hofman et al.

Milestone number: 7

Milestone title: Structure, functionality and data input and output requirements of the Global Health Risk Assessment Toolbox defined

Lead beneficiary: WU (and MU and UU)

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REPORT INFORMATION

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Milestone Title	Structure, functionality and data input and output requirements of the Global Health Risk Assessment Toolbox defined
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Content

General structure	4
TOOL I: Testing procedures and results database for (eco)toxicity of PPP mixtures	5
TOOL II: Reference database of the models used	5
TOOL III: Estimations of PPP input and environmental distribution and reality check (soil – water – air) .6	
III.A: CSS results presentation	6
III.B: Regional and national maps	6
III.C: EU-level maps	7
TOOL IV: Exposure, hazard, and risk estimations and maps (from CSS to regional to EU-level)	7
IV.A: Terrestrial ecosystems	8
IV.B: Aquatic ecosystems	8
IV.C: Farm animals	8
IV.D: Humans	9
TOOL V: Integrated health impact	9
TOOL VI: Libraries of existing tools and data	9

General structure

The toolbox is composed from tools which are interlinked and have inner structure (see details below). The overall scheme is followed by a detailed description of each tool.

TOOL I: Testing procedures and results database for (eco)toxicity of PPP mixtures

This will be a “static” (i.e. non-interactive) tool including i) procedures and recommendations for the ecotoxicological and toxicological tests developed in SPRINT, and ii) a simple database of ecotoxicological and toxicological data presenting mainly the results of mixture testing in WP4 and based on the literature. This tool will be a structured and commented storage of documents and a database of results enabling visualization and interpretation by tool users.

Potential end-users	EFSA, PPP national authorities, policy makers, optionally industry and scientists
Internal inputs	documents and results from WP4 (M5+M6; D4.1 – D4.5) as well as from literature surveys
External inputs	literature survey
Other needs	expertise from WP4 and IT
End date	Aug 2023
Start date	early 2023
Priority	moderate
Risks	low
Start with	detailed procedure descriptions

TOOL II: Reference database of the models used

This tool will be a list of the models applied at some of the CSS, both fate and exposure models. For fate models, these include PRZM, TOXSWA, BROWSE, WINDHERO & OBOdustpred. For exposure models, these include Merlin-expo, TECearthworm and OBOexposure. USEtox (<https://usetox.org>) as integrated fate, exposure and effect model will also be added. It will be a user-friendly interface consisting of: links to the models applied, the fate and exposure scenarios developed at CSS, the input data needed (parameters, parameter’s sources, time series, etc.), together with explanations of the models, documentation, and possibly tutorials (e.g. examples from the CSS). We will also inform on the intended model usage.

Potential end-users	EFSA, PPP national authorities, policy makers, industry and scientists
Internal Inputs	the model’s meta-data and explanation from WP3 together with examples of applications at CSS, links to the model sources; WP3 deliverables 3.1 – 3.4
External Inputs	literature survey
Other needs	expertise from WP3, WP6, and IT
End date	mid 2023
Start date	March 2022
Priority	moderate
Risks	moderate
Start with	models already available (e.g. PEARL & OBO)

TOOL III: Estimations of PPP input and environmental distribution and reality check (soil – water – air)

This tool will provide estimates of PPP input (i.e. emissions – e.g. PPP usage data) into the environment at various spatial and temporal scales. Using these PPP usage estimates, the distribution of pesticides to the environmental compartments will be modelled and concentration maps will be created for soil, water, and air. The measured PPP concentrations will be used as “reality check” (to verify correctness of the modelled/estimated values), mainly using the CSS results presentation and also utilizing other available data (e.g. LUCAS soil monitoring, WFD monitoring etc.).

Potential end-users	EFSA, PPP national authorities, policy makers, decision makers, optionally industry and scientists
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III.A: CSS results presentation

In this tool, CSS monitoring plan will be highlighted and explained. The results of each CSS will be summarized (WP2 – D2.3 deliverable) and visualized: a summarized visualization of the results of the environmental and personal samples collected in each CSS and localized information about the results (countries with CSS and after clicking, the presentation of the aggregated results will be shown; the exact location where the samples come from, so study participants and farms, are not disclosed). The results from the CSS will be also extrapolated to the regional level.

Potential end-users	farmer associations, land managers
Internal inputs	monitoring plan (D2.1) and the CSS data on PPP distribution (D2.3) processed by descriptive analysis (WP2); data collected in review D2.2
External inputs	literature (within review D2.2 resulting in database)
Requirements	expertise from WP2 (analytical experts, data processing & interpretation of the measured results), WP5 (data processing & interpretation of the toolbox presented results), WP8 (data visualization and communication), CSS leaders (interpretation and communication), and IT (incorporation in web platform)
End date	end 2022
Start date	Mar 2022
Priority	high
Risks	medium
Start with	concept for one CSS

III.B: Regional and national maps

The maps will visualize predicted PPP input (i.e. emissions - e.g. PPP usage data) to the environment (in line with D5.2 – generalized PPP application patterns) and modelled PPP concentrations in the environmental compartments (soil-water-air), together with a tabular overview of the mapped data and explanation of the calculations. The uncertainty of the predictions will be carefully indicated or discussed where possible. The focus will be primarily on the data-rich countries (e.g. Netherlands, Czech Republic). These countries are considered to have very good spatial (high resolution) and temporal (different years) data, such as i) crop types and their location; ii) pesticide usage, including frequency and quantity applied; iii) several weather stations.

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Internal inputs	CSS results and their regional extrapolation (tool III.A) to check the estimates with the reality
External inputs	PPP usage data (active substance and crop specific) for given geographical areas, PPP application data (rate, composition, BBCH...), spatial and temporal crop data for given geographical areas, PPP properties database, other relevant data (meteorological, pedological etc.) collected for selected countries
Requirements	CSS leaders (help in collecting the national data and linking to national PPP authorities); WP3 (fate and exposure); WP6 (LCIA emission modelling); GIS experts; IT (incorporation in web platform either static maps or dynamic)
End date	mid 2023
Start date	March 2022
Priority	high
Risks	high
Start with	NL & CZ PPP input estimates + M8 (relevant European data for upscaling)

III.C: EU-level maps

The maps will show estimates of PPP emissions and related environmental concentrations at European level, together with an overview of the mapped data. Global PPP use data will be combined with a spatial fate model. Nationally reported application data and predicted inputs (IIIB) will be used as cross-validation with this approach.

Internal inputs	national-level data (tool IIIB) and additional field data (e.g. from CSS) for cross-validation; TBD
External inputs	input data for LCIA emission model at EU scale; TBD
Requirement	WP6 (LCIA emission assessment expertise); WP3 (fate and exposure); GIS experts; IT (incorporation in web platform either static maps or dynamic)
End date	mid 2024
Start date	March 2022
Priority	low
Risks	high
Start with	collection of the needed data, TBD

TOOL IV: Exposure, hazard, and risk estimations and maps (from CSS to regional to EU-level)

In this task, concentrations in the various compartments of the environment will be used for the exposure assessment and the exposure outputs will be compared with the hazard data to map the risk for each substance for terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, animals, and humans. With respect to animals and humans, environmental exposure will be complemented by dietary exposure assessment using additional data on feed and food from existing databases (e.g. EFSA records).

Potential end-users	EFSA, PPP national authorities, policy makers, regulators, decision makers, industry and scientists
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IV.A: Terrestrial ecosystems

This will include a combination of the exposure data (measured results at CSS level and predicted environmental concentrations at national and EU-level) for the soil compartment and available hazard data followed by assessment of ecological risks for terrestrial organisms, mainly soil microorganisms, earthworms and other soil invertebrates, beneficial insects, bees and non-target plants. The calculated risks will be plotted on maps (at national and EU-level) or presented into the CSS results visualization.

Internal inputs	environmental concentration predictions (tool III); CSS data; WP4 data;
External inputs	ecotoxicological data (databases, EFSA reports, literature ...)
Requirements	WP4 (ecotoxicity and ecological risk assessment); GIS (mapping); IT (incorporation in web platform either static maps or dynamic)
End date	end 2023 (CSS); early 2025 (national and EU-level)
Start date	now (CSS); end 2023 (national and EU-level)
Priority	high (CSS); medium (national and EU-level)
Risks	low
Start with	reproduction of earthworms

IV.B: Aquatic ecosystems

This will include a combination of the exposure data (measured results at CSS level and predicted environmental concentrations at national and EU-level) for the aquatic compartment and available hazard data followed by assessment of ecological risks for aquatic organisms, mainly fish, invertebrates and plants. The calculated risks will be plotted on maps (at national and EU-level) or presented into the CSS results visualization.

Internal inputs	environmental concentration predictions (tool III); CSS data; WP4 data;
External inputs	ecotoxicological data (databases, EFSA reports, literature ...)
Requirements	WP4 (ecotoxicity and ecological risk assessment); GIS (mapping); IT (incorporation in web platform either static maps or dynamic)
End date	end 2023 (CSS); early 2025 (national and EU-level)
Start date	now (CSS); end 2023 (national and EU-level)
Priority	high (CSS); medium (national and EU-level)
Risks	low
Start with	effects on fish

IV.C: Farm animals

This tool will include a compilation of results (at CSS level) and a probabilistic risk calculator.

Internal inputs	CSS data on farm animals
External inputs	information on animals (e.g., weight, type, etc.) and animal feed; TBD
Requirements	expertise from WP4, WP5, and IT, the Q2 (WP2) on livestock
End date	end 2023 (CSS); early 2025 (national and EU-level)
Start date	now (CSS); end 2023 (calculator)
Priority	high (CSS); medium (national and EU-level)
Risks	low (CSS); medium (national and EU-level)
Start with	selected animal

IV.D: Humans

This tool will include a compilation of results and comparison with acceptable daily intake (at CSS level) and maps of hazard indices or increased risk at national and European level.

Internal inputs	CSS level: participants info (weight, age, etc) per CSS and PPP concentrations from WP3 models
External inputs	population exposure distribution (also mixtures) Env & Diet / Exposure-response functions (input from literature & WP4)
Requirements	expertise from WP2, WP3, WP5, WP4, WP6, and IT
End date	Oct 2024 (CSS); early 2025 (maps)
Start date	Jan 2022 (CSS); March 2022 (maps)
Priority	high (CSS); medium (national and EU-level)
Risks	low (CSS); medium (national and EU-level)
Start with	reproduction / health outcomes; start with diet

TOOL V: Integrated health impact

This tool will consist of an integrated risk assessment in which all the impacts and risks (from tool IV) will be combined together. Specific approaches and inputs (beyond those available from tool IV) to create this tool need to be identified.

Internal inputs	EFSA, policy makers, regulators, industry and scientists
External inputs	
Requirements	literature and also approach for integrated risk assessment from various stakeholders (EFSA, ECHA, OECD, UNEP, WHO ...)
Other needs	expertise from WP5 and IT and others
End date	TBD
Start date	March 2022
Priority	medium
Risks	high
Start with	literature review of existing approaches and a delineation of the methodology

TOOL VI: Libraries of existing tools and data

In this tool, a structured database of other existing tools and important sources of PPP related data (with links and short explanations) will be provided.

Potential end-users	EFSA, policy makers, regulators, industry and scientists
Internal inputs	SPRINT SOLES, scoping reviews, systematic reviews
External inputs	list of available tools and related links and documentation
Requirements	will be collected in parallel as "by-product" when building the other tools
End date	end 2023
Start date	now
Priority	low
Risks	low
Start with	tools collected for the Frankfurt meeting